

1 MARCH 2022

Press Release

NEW NIGHTWORKER CHARTER SEEKS TO IMPROVE CONDITIONS FOR NIGHTTIME WORKERS

A NIGHTWORKSHOP INITIATIVE

PRESS RELEASE

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A new charter has been released on Zero Discrimination Day (1 March), seeking to improve working conditions for night workers.

The [Nightworker Charter](#), launched by campaigner Julius-Cezar MacQuarie, aims to offer practical solutions for improving the working conditions of nightworkers.

Night workers are essential to our economy, from our emergency services to public transport. But the current labour system is designed for daytime work. This means that the problems facing nighttime workers are rarely recognised, let alone fixed. Launched on 1 March, the Nightworker Charter highlights the need to recognise the contribution of all nightworkers in our societies. It will seek to put nighttime workers on equal footing with their daytime counterparts.

The charter upholds the basic rights of nightworkers to live and work in dignity.

These employees are essential to keeping our societies going around-the-clock.

Recognising that night work is its own form of work with specific dynamics and problems, especially in post-industrial countries, is long overdue.

There are millions of people – including migrants, women, and People of Colour – who work ‘graveyard’ shifts at night. Poor working conditions mean many of these people experience ill health, isolation, and exclusion from mainstream society. For example, some have to eat fast food as there are no other options and working all night can disrupt circadian and biological rhythms. Not being able to socialise with friends during the daytime and evenings marginalises nightworkers even further.

Nightworkers, also known as the ‘other 9-5’ workers, frequently live on the margins of mainstream society, meaning they are

often unable to attend family events. Too often, they are absent from the minds of those in government who tackle problems in other forms of work.

The COVID-19 pandemic has shown how across the European Union and in the UK, despite their strategic roles in the functioning of national economies, nightworkers have been excluded from political agendas and public debates about who is an 'essential' or 'key' worker. Nightworkers deserve a better social contract – better food, sleep, remuneration, transport, and rest places when they toil at night.

These workers are left spent and exhausted by the merciless 24/7 demand for manual labour that keeps the world going around the clock, even in times of crisis.

The Nightworkers Charter role offers fresh and concrete ways to recognise, to address, and repair the problems faced by those working in the nighttime economy.

There is a pressing demand for a new set of arrangements that addresses the problems specific to nightwork. This charter will seek to improve the lives of night workers by repairing a broken labour system that causes suffering for millions of these individuals and their families and friends.

You can view and [sign the Nightworker Charter here.](#)

Contact Julius-Cezar MacQuarie, who founded the Nightworker Charter, for more information on imailfromdrjc@gmail.com / imacarie@nec.ro

Background information

What is the Nightworker Charter?

The Nightworker Charter seeks to improve the working conditions of nightworkers.

The Nightworker Charter gives nightworkers the voice and tools to gain recognition for their many contributions to national economies.

What does the Nightworker Charter do?

The Nightworker Charter offers practical solutions to improve

nightworkers' working conditions on the basis that all relevant stakeholders:

- (1) Recognise the problems specific to nightwork
- (2) Address the multi-layered precarity associated with nightwork
- (3) Make nightwork a stand-alone form of work in legal terms

Why is the Nightworker Charter relevant now?

Nightworkers play a crucial role in supporting nighttime economies (NTE), day workers, and national economies throughout Europe. Yet today we all face a health crisis. This Nightworker Charter represents solidarity with nightshift workers, be they the frontline or even the 'non-essential' workers who have helped us get through this awful period. The Nightworker Charter begins a reparation process that defends nightworkers' rights embedded within current constitutional arrangements but are hardly ever implemented.

How did the Nightworker Charter come about?

For the past decade, I have reached out to the many people who inhabit the night. I do this in my various capacities: as a night ethnographer, migration scholar, outreach worker, and collaborator with NGOs that work with vulnerable groups. I do this because I care about the vulnerable migrants and locals doing hidden, yet essential labour – and that's why I think you should help.

The ideas behind this Nightworker Charter have developed through my conversations with individuals and organisations who also care about those working the invisible nightshift.

The Nightworker Charter remains open to collaboration with individuals and organisations pledging to improve conditions for those who work nights.

How can you get involved?

Individuals and organisations are invited to sign this charter and invite others to do the same. Recommend the charter to unions, labour organisations, employers, local and regional

councillors, and health and safety organisations, councillors,
and health and safety organisations.

THE FOLLOWING REVIEWERS, TRANSLATORS AND EDITORS DESERVE SPECIAL MENTION:

FOR PUBLISHING AND COPY-EDITING THIS PRESS RELEASE

Christoph Laimer | *dérive* Magazine

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